

An Analysis Of Culture And Ethnicity As Problems For National Integration In Nigeria

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Abstract:

This paper examines the problem with Nigeria as it regards to the role of culture and ethnicity in national integration. There are about 250 ethnic groups in Nigeria. These ethnic groups have diverse cultures and ideologies; different languages and belief systems; though these ethnic groups co-exist in one country – Nigeria. There are series of problems earmarked for them. Their co-existence is characterized by ethnocentrism and nepotism. These forces have made it impossible for these ethnic groups to agree with one voice without any feeling marginalized; hence the issue of power and resource sharing formula. Culture is another problem which makes integration so difficult in Nigeria, as there are diverse cultural practices that sever one from each other. This paper therefore seeks to examine how culture and ethnicity have become problematic to national integration. It also examines how ethnicity and cultural bias have fuelled corruption, indiscipline, injustice which constitutes major challenges to national integration. Suggestions on possible solutions to these problems include: youths involvement in leadership, job opportunity for unemployed youths and there will be equity in everything we share in common.

Key words: Nigeria, Culture, Ethnicity and Problem of Integration

Introduction

Nigeria is a country that is thickly populated with about 194, 499,199 people, according to United Nations estimation by the year 2018 with about 250 ethnic groups; yet none of these groups constitutes the majority of the people's population. However there are three major ethnic groups in Nigeria- Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba, among all the other ethnic groups categorized as minority groups such as Kanuri, Efik, Itsekiri etc. Each of these groups has their own culture, language,

ideology and custom. Amidst of these diversity, issue of national integration has become an uphill task, following ethnicity and cultural bias. Uju (2000:186) quoted Schwarz (1963:2) "and observed that some of these minority ethnic groups had no historical relationship with the dominant group in their regions, others were enslaved, still others were once secured in their "proud kingdoms, and some recall an earlier day when they and their city-states far outshone the villages of their dominant neighbours of today" Nigeria

is made up of 36 states including the Federal Capital Territory (Abuja). It is politically divided into six geopolitical zones of North East, North West, North Central, South East, South West and South South. Each geopolitical zone has identical culture which makes them different from one another.

Conceptual Clarification:

Culture

Culture is defined by many people in different ways. People and Bailey (1994:21), as quoted by Agbo (2018:169), see culture as, “the whole way of life of some group of people”. That is to say that culture is the people’s way of life. It is their ideologies about everything in life such as pattern of dressing, and the type of dance attributed to them, their style of greetings, the way they speak and the way they approach things. Culture even affects ones reasoning hence people will wake up one day and decided to kill people and they now start immediately to wage war with other people without looking back or think of after effect. Ikwemesi (2012:132) described culture as coeval realities with the society and that the legitimacy of each derives from the other. This is why Ugwu (2014:52) described Nigeria as “a state of crises which has almost defiled all possible solutions”. Some of these problems emanate from people’s culture which they would want other people to imbibe

whether suitable or not. This now poses problem to the nation because people’s opinion must be respected. Anichebe (2010:233) sees culture as the totality of a people’s way of life and that culture is made up of material and non-material aspects. The material aspects are the physical objects while the non-materials are: ideas, beliefs, feelings, values, and norms etc. “It is now accepted that culture as a way of life is both dynamic and static” (Egonu, 2001:315). Egonu went ahead to describe the dynamic and its static nature and said, that it is dynamic when each succeeding generation may discover new norms and borrow from other cultures in the process of adapting to changing times and circumstances thereby enriching the cultural heritage; then static, in the sense that there is the spirit of a culture which guarantees its serenity while absorbing all adaptations and borrowings and ensuring their integration and stability within the culture. Gustav Klamm in Enebe (2018:231) see culture as “the customs, information and skill, domestic and public life in peace and war, religion, science, and art, manifested in the transmission of past experience to the new generation” Finally, no culture is superior to the other just as language, hence there are people who make use of it and it is equally beneficial to them. However, people’s culture helps a lot in molding of character especially the young ones who may not understand the essence why culture should hold to certain values.

Culture is good in an essence but it shall not go beyond limit. People's way of life has to be respected especially those that feel concerned, nevertheless should not creep into other people's culture to determine or influence other people's life. People have right to live and by exhibiting ones culture, should not take other people's life. Otherwise that will be a bridge of individual's right. People live and respect their culture which works and guide the people hence different cultures as Nigeria is diverse in nature.

Ethnicity

Ethnicity is a derivative of ethnic group. According to Osaghae (1994:44) ethnicity is "problematic phenomenon whose character is conflictual rather than consensual". Ethnicity is an emotional charged group (Abedin, 2012:01). This is true as the group is always charged whenever it comes to anything concerning their ethnic group. It is united by a force which moves people from doing certain imaginable thing which ordinarily would not believe they can do it. It is the characteristics exhibited by the ethnic group. It is a product of conscious effort by social actors. Then ethnic group according to Osaghae (1994) is the group with ascribed membership, usually but not always based on claims or myths of common history and ancestry. They are mostly regarded as those that have common identity. Such as

language, character, style of dressing, style of greeting, sometimes religion will come into play. Linguistic differences often pose serious problem for national integration. Abedin (2012:8) stated that, "the people who speak same language often develop a strong separatist or parochial or corporate sentiment. As a result, a multi-lingual area or population usually divides itself into various linguistic regions or groups which develop what sociologist often refer to as "we" and "they" attitude or perceptions". Achebe (1983:45) quoted a scientist who said that every ethnic group is of course something of a problem for Nigeria's easy achievement of cohesive nationhood. But in actual sense they were referring to Igbo who they see as a thorn in their flesh. The Igbo people looks as they are in minority because of the defeat they suffered during Biafra/Nigeria civil war. Nevertheless Nigeria cannot do without Igbo as long as Nigeria remains one nation.

Many nations have tackled ethnic problem and tried to accommodate one another such as part of Asia as recorded by Achebe(1983) but some still battle with the problem of peaceful co-existence, such that is witnessed in Nigeria. Sometimes one should not blame those that agitate. For instance when it comes to sharing formula, these are things that border so many Igbo people and some other Nigerians. The injustice play in Nigeria when it comes to admission, some

people will be favoured while some will be ill-treated. For instance, this is the record of 2018 National Common Entrance Examination

result released, here is the cut off mark for each state as follows:

State	Male	Female
Abia	65	65
Adamawa	40	40
Akwa-Ibom	63	63
Anambra	66	66
Bauchi	18	18
Bayelsa	51	51
Benue	60	60
Borno	33	33
Cross Rivers	54	54
Delta	65	65
Ebonyi	60	60
Edo	63	63
Ekiti	62	62
Enugu	65	65
Gombe	32	37
Imo	66	66
Jigawa	37	37
Kaduna	52	52
Kano	34	34
Katsina	37	37
Kebbi	35	35
Kogi	61	61
Kwara	62	62
Lagos	65	61
Nassarawa	42	42
Niger	49	49
Ogun	65	65
Ondo	64	64

Osun	64	64
Oyo	63	63
Plateau	52	52
Rivers	62	62
Sokoto	15	07
Taraba	19	19
Yobe	20	20
Zamfara	14	12
FCT Abuja	57	57

How can one account for this disparity in the state cut off marks? Why shouldn't people agitate in how they are treated hence they all are in the same nation, took the same examination and all that. Why the disparity in the admission criteria? This is just one example of such disparities. It even extended to University admission criteria. Some states would have least score while some would be high. This disparity makes some ethnic groups feel cheated and also feel that they cannot be integrated. Achebe (1983:1) clearly stated that the problem with Nigeria lies in leadership. Nobody wants to admit the truth. Achebe went on to sight one example of disciplined leader Nigeria had to prove his claim and said,

“On the morning, after Murtala Muhammed seized power in July 1975, public Servants in Lagos were found “on seat” at seven-thirty in the morning.

Even the “go-slow” traffic that had defeated every solution and defied every regime vanished overnight from the streets! Why? The new ruler's reputation for ruthlessness was sufficient to transform in the course of only one night the style and habit of Nigeria's unruly capital. That the character of one man could establish that quantum change in a people's social behaviour was nothing less than miraculous. But it shows that social miracles can happen”.P1

This could not continue for the head of States was assassinated because he wants equity to reign. Impunity and injustice started in earnest and people sing praises to evil not minding what people will say. People's conscience now sour because of little gratification received from the corrupt individuals. This is why some good people of Nigeria would not talk because they may

be silenced just like Murtala Muhammed. This notwithstanding, the legacy left is still living, speaking for him. He fought the battle but he was betrayed just like Julius Ceaser who was stabbed by his best friend, Brutus.

Enebe (2018:231) listed the mechanisms of national integration as the executive, judiciary, legislature, the constitution, federal character, national youth service scheme, educational institution and religion. All these are mechanisms devised by the federal republic to help in national integration but people now turn round to use them to disintegrate the nation. "They now begin to focus the eyes of followership on the fruits of the national association, the so called 'national cake' and the method of sharing and not of baking it".

National Integration

National integration is coming together of a nation toward progress. Simply put, it is the closeness of a nation. Encyclopedia Britannica defined National Integration as "the process whereby a series of conscious and unconscious efforts are made in order to achieve a sense of nationhood" p582. This means that a lot of sacrifice should be made in order to get this done. Most often, the smaller political group or ethnic group had to forfeit their

rights and privileges and embrace the larger group system or idea so that the nation can move on progressively. This is very difficult to achieve. That is why Nigeria is now in trouble having refused to allow the Herdsmen to occupy peoples' land for cattle grazing, seeing the havoc the Herders are causing to the society. Many states in Nigeria refused to release their lands for grazing. After all, that is a private business of some people. Why must they take land free of charge? They make money from the business. This is a very serious issue in Nigeria where the bourgeoisie oppress the poor and yet nothing happens. If this is the integration, most people would prefer disintegration to have peace than to integrate and remain in penury. Shehu Sani, a senator representing Kaduna Central in National Assembly on Monday, 4th of June, 2018 told the president Muhammadu Buhari through the programme - 'road map' to free himself from cabals. Sani opined that Nigerians have never been divided as they are now. People no longer see themselves as one. They now see themselves as northern Nigeria and southern Nigeria; Muslims and Christians (Channel Television).

On September 21, 2016, the Daily Sun reported the attack of Aku people in Igbo-Etiti L.G.A of Enugu State by the Herdsmen, killing one man and kidnapped

two others. They also threatened to deal with the community if their demands are not met. The Herdsmen claimed that their 300 cows were stolen by Aku people and 10 other cows slaughtered by the Aku community. This allegation was based on assumption because after the investigations by the Divisional Police Officer (D.P.O) of the area, it was noted that those Herdsmen were not even camped in Aku that they camped at the boundary between Affa and Agu-Egede in Udi L.G.A. The traditional ruler of a community in Aku, Igwe V.O. Attah raised an alarm after he heard what the leader of the Herdsmen Alhaji Sadiq said, of imminent attack on the Aku community. Igwe of Aku community knew that since Alhaji Sadiq openly accused them that they must definitely carry out the oppression if measures are not taken. This is just an attempt to penetrate into the community for grazing according to the traditional ruler. Is that how people can forcefully taken what belongs to another person? The same Newspaper reported that this incident occurred barely after five months these herders attacked Ukpabi and Nimbo in Uzo-Uwani L.G.A on Tuesday, 26 April, 2016 during the mid-night. They raided the villagers and killed so many people including a youth corp. member that was serving in the area and also wounded so many others. Is this how one should

accept one to live with? The truth must be told. Onuoha (2000) has this to say:

Is there anything inherent in the nature of the Nigerian State? That generates political instability? More fundamentally, how can our understanding of the nature of the Nigerian States help us to make informed predictions about the Fourth Republic? These questions have been necessitated by the worsening political instability; we mean any threat to the stability of the Nigerian state. Within a short period of 39 years, The Nigerian state has recorded more political crises and instability than any other state in Africa. As Ofoeze (1990) observed, Nigeria's existence as a polity has been characterized by mutual suspicion, distrust, and hatred among the various ethnic groups...p198.

Early in the morning on 24th day of April, 2018, a group of people suspected to be herdsmen invaded a Roman Catholic Church in Benue state killing two Catholic priests and 17 parishioners totaling 19 people who were worshipping in the church(Channel TV News 24/4/18). God forbid. It is high time the international community should arise to speak for the poor masses in Nigeria. Darkness has engulfed the Nigerian nation.

There are things that would make the National Integration almost impossible in Nigeria if not carefully addressed. These are: Corruption, Indiscipline, and Injustice. There are other things but most of them are embedded on these three as they manifest.

Corruption

Ikejiani (1995) see corruption as a deviation from honest; influenced by bribery; to induce, to act dishonestly and to destroy the integrity of man. This is the main canker- worm that burrowed the hearts of Nigerians. This is seen in the people's quest for money. It is corruption that gave rise to indiscipline and injustice. If there is no corruption, there will be no indiscipline and injustice. Nwachukwu(1987:21) observed that every Nigeria is corrupt in one way or the order. Nwachukwu thus observed that it is almost impossible to get any document signed in any office without giving kick back or receiving one. Then how can truth come out if this is so? Nwagwu (2011) says:

Corruption in Nigeria has passed the alarming and entered the fatal stage; and Nigeria will die if we keep pretending that she is only slightly indisposed... Nigerians are corrupt because the system under which they live today makes corruption easy and

profitable; they will cease to be corrupt when corruption is made difficult inconvenient.p4

Consequently, Achebe (1983) challenged the statement of Shagari, former president of Nigeria, who said that corruption in Nigeria has not gotten to alarming stage. Achebe vehemently retorted and said;

anybody who can say that corruption in Nigeria has not yet become alarming is either a fool, a crook or else does not live in this country. Shagari is neither a fool nor a crook. So I must assume that he lives abroad. Which is not as strange or fanciful as some might think? Many Presidents, especially Third world Presidents, do not live in their country. One of the penalties of exalted power is loneliness. Harnessed to the tapings of protocol and blockaded by a buffer of grinning courtiers and sycophants, even a good and intelligent leader will gradually begin to forget what the real world looks like. When a President of Nigeria sets out to see things for himself, what does he actually see? p37.

A president is deceived to believing everything presented to him on the state of

his nation, without caring to make enquiries in the nation he is ruling. Once they hear that head of States is visiting, every pot-holes on the roads will be filled up as soon as those in authority knew the president will take that route or probably he may pretend not to have known so as to solidify his stay because ‘there are powers to be’ that is people who made him to be in that position as the president hence election malpractice. Therefore he should talk when he is allowed to talk. Otherwise the seat will be too hot for him to sit on. Corruption in Nigeria has reached a stage that Achebe (1983: 38) likening it to a goat that is preventing from eating yam. This means that it is now part of the system and the norm. He vividly ex-rayed corruption in Nigeria without any reservation and said that it is impossible and, even if possible, of little value to attempt a comprehensive picture of the types and scope of Nigerian corruption but rather most people will agree that corruption in Nigeria has variety, magnitude and brazenness since the beginning of the second republic and has been extravagantly fuelled by budgetary abuse and what Achebe called political patronage on an unprecedented scale. Public funds are shared with ignominy to political allies. Ugwu (2014:54) in his 84th inaugural lecture lamented that “Nigeria is experiencing a period of serious threat of extinction by corruption”. He believed that

in every sphere of life of a Nigerian that there must be a wide spate of corruptible practices among the people. This is serious that every Nigerian should seat up and rethink for self discipline otherwise people outside world would not want to have any serious business with a Nigerian. On 3rd of April, 2018, there was a report by Channel Television that over 170,000 people were displaced in Benue state by the Herdsmen, and the Inspector General of Police was given order by the president concerning that but the order was flouted and nothing was done by the president. Is government sincere in what they are doing? This is a height of insincerity and corruption in the highest order. IGP was appointed by the president and a brother Muslim. If he disobeys him, the president; he knows what to do to put him right. All these prangs as the Igbo people would say, is covering face with basket and pretending not to be seeing while you see everything.

Indiscipline

This is an indecent behaviour. Some people cannot do without indiscipline. It does seems as if it is now a norm. It is in every category of people. People most often break protocol in order to show superior to others. It is normal to serve food first to somebody who came first in a function to maintain orderliness; but when you do the

other way round it becomes indisciplined. Though there is no rule that says it must be so. People jump queue to be served first especially in filling stations when there are number of people queuing to get fuel. The so called ‘personality’ will just rush into the filling station and demand for fuel. In the presence of others, he will receive attention. Achebe (1983:28) narrated that an observer of our national scene might well be pardoned if he ran away with the impression that we were a country with an eccentric minority who can restrain themselves and an overwhelming majority who can’t! However, Achebe still believed that though Nigeria condition is critical, and also getting worse by day, there are still the majority, albeit dormant, who still have self control. This spirit of indisciplined would be difficult to call for integration since the individual would first check how beneficial it will be to him or his people.

Culture is one of the mechanisms for national integration as National Youths Service Scheme was created in 1973 to make the young school leavers have opportunity to socialize with other cultural group other than his/her own area before the person settles down in life; but culture most often times brings antagonism amongst Nigerians; especially among the elderly people in Nigeria. Uwakwe (2018) says that culture severe relationship amongst youths

especially when it comes to marriage. Most parents do not agree to the union hence one party comes from other cultural area. This sometimes leads to indisciplined by the couple hence they may vow to be together as husband and wife. Parents will see it as disobedience and sometimes curse their children. Uwakwe (2018:20) opined that the distribution of national resources among the major groups often breeds discontent amongst the minority groups hence much financial and industrial control of the Nigerian economy is firmly held by the Yoruba because of the key industries sited in that area.

Language is one thing that manifest in culture which should be something that people should long to embrace as integral part of unity but people now discriminate among others as soon as they notice any difference in language spoken. Once people notice language difference and the way you greet or even dress, you will notice some signs that will make you realize that you are in a fist. Sometimes you may be deceived if you are making any enquiries from the indigenes. The Igbo saying goes like this. “onye amaghi, ibe ezi ya” meaning, when you don’t understand, another person will teach you. This is no longer the case.

Injustice

This is the deprivation of rightful position of someone and giving it to another in order to humiliate the former. There are cases of injustice in Nigeria which led to so many agitations. For instance when one forcefully drives another away from his/her home, burnt the houses and send the person away from his/her domain without any cogent reason and without apologies. This is a height of injustice which could amount to somebody's death. Herdsmen will kill and occupy peoples farmlands with crops, destroyed by their cattle and nothing will be done about it by the government as witnessed in so many places in Nigeria. How can one now speak about integration? In what way can such a wounded group be integrated? So many problems are locking heads together in the unity of the Nigerian nation. Do we talk about employment saga in Nigeria? It is for the well to do. The poor, after the university education would go back to menial jobs to put food on the table while the bourgeois will be getting employed in big establishments and firms. This will never make for easy integration. Unemployment problem is for the poor and not for the rich. Many people are being suppressed because they have nobody to speak for them. Yet the same fees are being taken from every student, there is no disparity when it comes to that.

Since the amalgamation of Nigeria in 1914, Nigeria has been in existence as a nation only on paper. There has been discrimination between the northerners and the southerners. Uju (2000) noted that;

The British did encourage social distance between the north and the south. It was believed that the more radical southerners would pollute the northerners who were more pliable and obedient to traditional authority. For this reason, the southerners who came to take up civil servile service jobs in the north because there were very few educated northerners then were meant to live in isolated areas known as 'Sabon Gari' or 'Strangers' Quarters' in the urban areas. Thus northerners were made to see southerners as strangers in the northern part of the same country and this has affected the relationship until today when southerners are required to take up contract and not permanent appointment in the northern states .p 188

What an injustice, in a nation where they are supposed to be one. Sometimes a junior person will come to head a senior person in an establishment yet the senior person will be doing the entire work because the senior person is the one that knows what to do. Nevertheless the junior person will still receive the fat salary against what it supposed to be. People pretend to be what they are not, deceiving people. This is the

statement of an elderly statesman who supposed to be the champion of the unity of the nation but see his hate speech as quoted by Uju (2000):

Many Nigerians deceive themselves by thinking that Nigeria is one, particularly some of the press people with the chance of writing in the papers to tell the world that Nigeria is one country. When I look around me here in this council, I see the chiefs and I am inclined to feel some presence of unity. But I am sorry to say that this presence of unity is an artificial one and it ends outside this chamber... These southern tribes who are now pouring into the North in ever-increasing numbers, and are more or less domicile here, do not mix with the Northern people...and we in the North look upon them as invaders.p189

It is obvious that anybody who is not welcomed should not integrate himself/herself with the community for fear of any eventuality. An Igbo adage says that 'it is only a tree that heard that it will be cut down and still remains in its former position'. This is why some of the southerners as quoted by an elderly statesman from the north are being careful about integrating proper with the northerners. Achebe (1983:6) described how ethnicity has robbed Dr. Nnamdi

Azikiwe his position by Chief Obafemi Awolowo and made him to go back to where he came from. This was because Zik was not a Yoruba man. Many people have been denied of an opportunity because of the cultural influence even though the person performed better than others who are indigenes.

Conclusion

There is nothing that has beginning that does not have an end. So also the problem with Nigeria can have an end. Amalgamation of southern and northern Nigeria was done in 1914. It is for a purpose which may be beneficial to every Nigeria. Ajah (2006:9) rightly stated that "national integration in Nigeria after independence was still not a choice; rather, it is a necessity". Ajah went on to explain why the nation Nigeria should remain one because of an agreement prior to independence that various ethnic groups and religious groups accepted to integrate with one another. Agreeing to abide by that would make them to have independence. Selfishness and favouritism should be damped to make Nigeria a great nation which it should be. It can be seen from the analysis that national integration will be difficult when basic needs such as: access, identity, autonomy, security and equity; compounded by bad leadership are experienced. Let Nigerians face reality that

hard work pays and not the opposite as stated by Onuoha (2000:209) who pointed out that, the surest way to conquer poverty is the seizure of state power; with it the person is instantly a hero, from there, you can now bless your friends and punish your enemies and loot the entire treasury and nothing will happen. This is in line with Burton's theory which is in agreement that conflict management is more effective if government is devoid of corruption (Burton 1997:75). Otherwise let Nigeria be restructured to maintain peace. The problem facing the nation is that the people who are expected to change the system are the people who are enjoying in the bad system. The question now is who will salvage the nation from total collapse?

Integration means to come together and become one. It has no other meaning when we are really talking about National integration. But the way things are going in Nigeria, I think the best option is to disintegrate. There is no need deceiving ourselves that Nigeria is one but far from the truth. "Afenfere and the Odua People's congress represent the Yoruba ethnic group, while the Ibos are represented by Ohanaeze Ndiigbo. The Arewa consultative forum has emerged as the defender of northern interests who feels threatened by the challenges to their power and identity, while the south-south people's assembly

speaks for the Niger Delta States" (Osinem et.al 2013). How can Nigeria be integrated with these vying groups that are always looking for where to fault. The ruling class, (bourgeoisie) keep on pressing hard to continue to rule and suppress people. When one realizes that nobody lives forever, one will allow peace reign, knowing full well that all these wealth being emancipate is vanity upon vanity.

Recommendation

The following recommendations are made to address the issue of ethnicity and culture in national integration: There should be equity in everything and not to faction out formula that would suit some sections of the nation.

The president on 31st May, 2018 signed a bill "not too young to run". Let this bill be seriously be implemented to enable the youths to participate in politics and allowing them in governance. This is not by mere signing the bill and not allowing them opportunity to rule. The president made a statement that they should wait until after 2019 election so that they would not work against him. I believe, this is a joke because they should be given opportunity to contest. Again anybody who is above sixty years of age should not contest for any election in Nigeria. This will pave way for the youths to come out and new ideas to be created.

There should be dialogue in everything where there is misunderstanding to have consensus. Even though a group may not be favoured in the agreement but for the peace to reign, such group would accept especially if they are given another opportunity where they will triumph. This agreement should be written and duly signed by groups concerned. If there is honesty in the agreement, definitely, things will work out fine.

Anybody who is holding any political position must create something that will generate revenue and equally create job opportunities for the youths especially those in state and federal houses, governors and president. Failure to achieve this in ones' first tenure should not venture to contest again. Again, no matter the achievement, nobody should contest for any position more than twice whether federal or state houses.

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